

more susceptible to infection than the other species tested; they were also morphologically similar to the rice plant.

Since the weeds are found growing in rice fields throughout the year, the fungus *C. sasakii* probably overwinters on them. The weed populations on bunds and hedges during the period of cultural operations would facilitate the pathogen's survival and help continue the disease cycle. The cycle could be easily interrupted by cleaning the bunds and eliminating graminaceous weeds, particularly *Echinochloa* species. ■

National symposium on sheath blight and blast in Madras, India

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Active rice research workers met at a 1-day symposium on the present understanding of sheath blight and blast diseases of rice at the Centre of Advanced Study in Botany, University of Madras, on 9 February 1979. The purpose was to review and discuss in depth the latest findings on the two important rice diseases.

Prof. A. Mahadevan, Centre director, welcomed the participants and observers. Dr. N. Parthasarathy, former director, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, presided, and H. K. Pande, CRRI director, delivered the keynote address.

Dr. Parthasarathy traced the history of rice and its pathology. Dr. Pande stressed the water technological aspects in augmenting yield. Two sessions were devoted to sheath blight and one to blast.

Dr. V. T. John presented an account of genetic resistance and chemical control of rice diseases. He suggested the use of artificially inoculated *Typha*-leaf bits as an alternate source of field inoculum for varietal screening against sheath blight. Most workers in screening trials use the stem-tape inoculation technique developed by Amin in 1975. Although cumbersome, the technique gives consistent results. Dr. John reported that such cultivars as ARC15672,

ARC18275, ARC18545, Ramedja, CET5656, and CET5952 are resistant. But it was suggested that they be listed as tolerant because no immune variety has been identified so far and the reactions of the cultivars vary from season to season. A fundamental paper on histopathological studies was presented by Dr. Manibhushan Rao. Fungi penetrate the host tissue through infectious lobate hyphae or by direct penetration through natural openings. The attraction toward somata-stomatal tropism caused a fivefold increase in penetration in susceptible cultivars.

A general account of the Indian work on sheath blight was reviewed by Dr. Premalata Dath. Her report that a phyllophane bacterium effectively inhibited the sheath blight parasite generated much interest. The subject should be further investigated. Kannaiyan and Prasad reported on soil amendments with neem cake and effective disease control. They also presented a comprehensive account of the physiology and host range of the pathogen. Sheath blight incidence at Maruteru was reported by Koteswara Rao, who suggested that intensive investigations on its control be started.

On blast, Dr. Sridhar stressed the role in resistance of antimicrobial substances (prohibitins) formed before infection and of those that increase in quantity after infection (phytoalexins). Little is known about phytoalexin production in rice. The question of considering as phytoalexins nomilactones A and B produced in rice leaves after blast infection was discussed in depth. Venkata Rao indicated that in 6 years of screening trials on blast conducted at Nellore, no correlation between leaf and neck blast incidence was found. Dr. John presented a general account of blast disease, emphasizing varietal resistance and fertilizer application.

Dr. Chakrabarthi closed the symposium with a special lecture on the perpetuation and spread of blast.

The participants repeatedly stressed that sheath blight has become significant in many rice-growing tracts. Conditions that predispose the sheath blight pathogen should be investigated. A clear

understanding of the host-pathogen interaction is lacking. Further work on the influence of cultural and environmental factors and of soil conditions on varietal resistance is needed.

The variability of *Pyricularia oryzae*, the causal organism of rice blast disease, is to be studied in detail. Genetic and cytologic investigations of the pathogen as well as epidemiologic studies including forecasting and warning systems should be made. A large-scale search for chemicals that induce systemic disease resistance in plants will be conducted. ■

Bleaching powder for bacterial blight control

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An attempt to control bacterial blight of rice with stable bleaching powder (SBP) containing 35% chlorine was made at Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, in 1078 kuruvai. The chemical was mixed with dry sand in a 4-1 ratio. The disease was assessed on variety TN1 in 5 hills/plot at the maximum tillering stage, the shoot blade stage, and 10 days after 50% flowering.

No disease was observed in the first two stages.

Disease incidence was not checked significantly when SBP was applied to the soil in a wet seedbed at 24 hours

Effect of stable bleaching powder (SBP) on bacterial blight control. Tamil Nadu, India.

Application of SBP at	Mean disease index (%)	Yield (t/ha)
5 ppm to soil 24 hours before seeding	54	1.1
30 ppm to nursery 24 hours before uprooting seedlings	47	0.8
5 ppm to seedbed, 30 ppm to nursery, and 50 ppm at panicle initiation	52	0.6
30 ppm to nursery and 50 ppm at panicle initiation	41	0.6
Control (untreated)	55	0.9